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Editorial: "Community centered digital libraries"

Anna Maria Tamaro

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Editorial: “Community centered digital libraries”

Digital Library Perspectives

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The papers in this issue of “Digital Library Perspectives” illustrate how digital libraries are adapting their services to become community-centered, fostering inclusive environments for learning and collaboration, promoting digital and artificial intelligence (AI) literacy and preserving cultural heritage.

Digital libraries can become community-centered by actively engaging users, adapting services to local needs and fostering inclusive environments that promote digital literacy and cultural preservation. The transformation of libraries from traditional information repositories to dynamic community hubs is essential in the digital age, where access to information and technology is crucial for social equity, inclusion and economic development.

Community-centered digital libraries are evolving to meet the diverse needs of their users by leveraging technology and fostering community engagement and participation. These digital libraries aim to provide accessible, collaborative and user-driven information services. One key way digital libraries can become more community-centric is by tailoring their offerings to the specific needs and characteristics of local populations. By creating environments that facilitate collaboration and interaction, libraries can strengthen community bonds and foster a sense of belonging among users. Digital literacy initiatives are another essential aspect of community-centered digital libraries. In addition to promoting digital literacy, these digital libraries can focus on preserving local culture and heritage.

Increasingly, community-centered digital libraries are integrating AI tools and infrastructure to foster collaborative, user-driven environments. In conclusion, community-centered digital libraries are well-positioned to meet the evolving needs of their communities.

Highlights from this issue:

“It answers questions that I didn’t know I had”: PhD students’ evaluation of an information-sharing knowledge graph.

Stanislava Gerdzheva (Department of Communication and Information Sciences, University of Hawai‘i at Manoa, Honolulu, Hawai‘i, USA).

Manjula Lamba (School of Information Sciences, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Champaign, Illinois, USA).

Interdisciplinary PhD programs can present significant challenges, as crucial information is often not readily accessible, being dispersed across various university websites. This study aims to introduce a knowledge graph that consolidates essential information on key categories (such as faculty, courses and dissertations) and their interrelationships, extracted from multiple sources, to meet the needs of interdisciplinary PhD students. It evaluates the usability of a participatory-designed knowledge graph, created to enhance information sharing and support decision-making.

Undergraduates’ experiences with library portal services: perceptions of usefulness and satisfaction

Adeike Elizabeth Ajisebutu (Department of Library and Information Science, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagan, Nigeria).

Adebowale Jeremy Adetayo (Department of Library and Information Science, Adeleke University, Ede, Nigeria).

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Martan Kehinde Alawajye (Nimbe Adedipe Library, Federal University of Abeokuta, Abeokuta, Nigeria).

Bosede Olufunmilayo Makinde (College of Medicine, Lagos State University, Ikeja).

This study aims to evaluate undergraduate students’ perceived usefulness and satisfaction with university library portal services in selected universities in South-West Nigeria. It contributes to the understanding of how these students perceive the utility and effectiveness of library portal services, emphasizing the need for these services to align with students’

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